

Macrocyclic Metal Complexes. Part-XVI. Nitrogen–Oxygen Donor Macrocyclic Metal Complexes of Nickel(II), Syntheses, Structure and Electron Transfer Reactions

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A series of nitrogen–oxygen donor macrocyclic complexes of nickel(II) of the type N_2O_2 and N_2O_3 has been investigated. The ligands and metal complexes have been characterised by ir, nmr and uv-vis spectrometry. The macrocycles undergo two-step reductions, $E_{1,2}^{\ddagger}$ values ranging from -1.0 to -1.2 V and $E_{1,3}^{\ddagger}$ values from -1.4 to -1.7 V. The first step of reduction has been attributed to the formation of a metal stabilised ligand anion radical. The magnitude of $E_{1,3}^{\ddagger}$ depends upon ligand structure.

NITROGEN donor macrocycles form strong complexes with the transition metal ions and post-transition metal ions^{1,2}. The other category of complexes involves polyether macrocycles of the crown type which are highly selective extractants for alkali and alkaline earth metal ions^{3,4}. In recent years, interaction of metal ions with ligands involving nitrogen and oxygen donor macrocycles are receiving attention⁵⁻¹¹ and these macrocycles are expected to be intermediate between crown ethers and aza macrocyclic ligands^{7,10,12}. However, electron transfer reactions of these macrocycles have not been explored through structural modification of ligands as well as metal ions. In continuation of our investigations^{13,14}, we report here some macrocyclic complexes containing oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms. The work reports the isolation of some new O_2N_2 donor macrocycles and their complexes on interaction with nickel(II) ion (1 and 2). The electrochemical properties of these macrocycles of nickel(II) have been studied along with some of the macrocyclic complexes of nickel(II) of the types 3–8, reported by Lindoy and coworkers⁷⁻¹⁰ so as to examine the effects of ligand field stabilisations and the associated structural factors on electron transfer behaviour. The ligand structures are presented in Scheme 1.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde, 1,2-dibromoethane, 1,3-dibromopropane and diethylenetriamine were B.D.H. reagents, and diethylenetriamine was distilled before use.

1, 4-Bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1, 4-dioxabutane, $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$: A solution of salicylaldehyde (24.4 g, 0.2 mol) in DMSO (120 ml) was added to an aqueous solution (200 ml) of sodium hydroxide (8 g, 0.2 mol) and the mixture was warmed. The warm solution was treated with 1,2-dibromoethane (18.4 g, 0.1 mol) in DMSO (120 ml). The resulting solution was refluxed under nitrogen for about 12 h and

Scheme 1

was allowed to stand at 0° . The resulting cream coloured crystals were washed with water and recrystallised from ether–chloroform mixture, ($\sim 40\%$), m.p. 129° (lit. 129°).

1, 5-Bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1, 5-dioxapentane, $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$: It was prepared in a similar way using 1,3-dibromopropane. The macrocyclic ligands 1 and 2 were synthesised by using the dialdehydes and diethylenetriamine and one such preparation is described here.

5, 6 : 16, 17-Bzo₂[17]-5, 7, 14, 16-tetraene-8, 11, 14-N₂-1, 4-O₂, $C_{20}H_{22}N_2O_2$: An alcoholic solution of freshly distilled diethylenetriamine (1.0 g, 0.01 mol; 30 ml absolute methanol) was added to an alcoholic solution of 1,4-bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,4-

dioxabutane (2.7 g, 0.01 mol; 150 ml absolute methanol) in a dropwise manner. The solution was then refluxed for 3 h. On cooling, the compound was obtained in the form of a suspension and the cold suspension was added to water (200 ml). On standing at 0°, the resulting light yellow crystals were washed with water and recrystallised from ether; m.p. 143°.

Preparation of the macrocyclic complexes was achieved either by the direct reaction of the macrocyclic ligand with nickel(II) or, by *in situ* procedure. Two exemplary preparations are described here.

$Ni[Bzo_2[17]tetraeneN_3O_2](ClO_4)_2, NiC_{20}H_{28}N_3O_2(ClO_4)_2$: A solution of macrocyclic ligand $Bzo_2[17]tetraeneN_3O_2$ (3.3 g, 0.01 mol) in butanol (50 ml) was added to the nickel(II) salt ($Ni(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$; 3.6 g, 0.01 mol) in butanol (50 ml). The mixture was stirred and heated for 30 min. The resulting light yellow solid was washed with butanol, then with ether and dried under reduced pressure.

$Ni[Bzo_2][17]tetraeneN_3O_2]Br_2, NiC_{20}H_{28}N_3O_2Br_2$: A solution of nickel(II) bromide (2.1 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in butanol (50 ml), was added to a solution of the precursor ligand 1,4-bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,4-dioxabutane (2.7 g, 0.01 mol; 100 ml of butanol). A hot butanolic solution of diethylenetriamine (1.0 g, 0.01 mol) was added then dropwise with stirring to the above solution, stirred and heated further for 2 h. The resulting blue coloured solid was washed with butanol, then with ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Elemental analyses of the compounds were found satisfactory.

Results and Discussion

Williamson condensation of salicylaldehyde with dibromoalkanes, namely, 1,2-dibromoethane and 1,3-dibromopropane in dimethylsulphoxide medium under nitrogen atmosphere yields the corresponding dialdehyde, 1,4-bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,4-dioxabutane and 1,5-bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,5-dioxapentane respectively containing two ethereal oxygen atoms on the backbone of the molecule. The dialdehydes in turn react with diethylenetriamine to give the macrocycles **1** and **2** respectively. Alternatively, in the *in situ* process in butanol medium, the dialdehyde appears to complex with the metal ion where the ketonic groups suffer from polarisation to provide a kinetic-controlled pathway for Schiff base condensation with the diamine. In order to avoid polymerisation high dilute conditions are required during the preparation of the complexes.

Infrared spectra: Salicylaldehyde exhibits a strong and broad band at 3250 cm^{-1} due to either inter- or intra-molecular hydrogen bonded OH stretching vibrations. This band disappears in the vibrational spectra of the intermediate dialdehydes demonstrating condensation of OH group of the salicylaldehyde with 1,2-dibromoethane or 1,3-dibromopropane with elimination of hydrogen

bromide. The aldehydic $\nu_{C=O}$ band observed at $\sim 1666\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for salicylaldehyde moves to a higher frequency region and appears with its intensity and characteristic structure at $\sim 1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the macrocycles, the characteristic $\nu_{C=O}$ band completely disappears and a relatively sharp band of medium intensity appears at $\sim 1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which originates due to the stretching vibrations of the newly introduced (C=N) groups.

The phenolic ν_{C-O} band in salicylaldehyde at $\sim 1325\text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappears from this position in the intermediate dialdehydes. In the dialdehydes two new bands appear at ~ 1275 and 1075 cm^{-1} which are attributed to the ethereal asymmetric and symmetric C-O-C stretching vibrations respectively. In the macrocycles these bands persist with minor shifts in their relative positions. A sharp band at $3350-3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is clearly perceptible in the N_3O_2 macrocycles which is generated from the secondary amine stretching modes. The vibrational bands affected on complexation are associated with the stretching mode of vibrations of secondary NH, imine (C=N) and ethereal vibrations, all of which undergo bathochromic shifts due to withdrawal of the electronic charge from nitrogen and oxygen atoms to the metal ion.

The spectral informations thus provide unequivocal evidence to postulate incorporation of the metal ion into the ring and coordinated to ring nitrogen and oxygen atoms, N_3O_2 , the macrocycle spanning in a square-pyramidal array.

Nmr spectra: The nmr spectral data are summarised in Table 1. The precursor dialdehyde, 1,4-bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,4-dioxabutane shows two signals at δ 4.54 and 10.4 occur as singlets due to CH_2 and CHO protons respectively. Another signal appearing as a multiplet at δ 7-8 has been assigned to the aromatic protons. The precursor intermediate 1,5-bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,5-dioxapentane shows two signals, a quintet and a triplet at δ 2.45 and 4.3 respectively. The quintet is assigned to methylene protons adjacent to ethereal carbon atoms. The triplet arises from the pair of equivalent methylene protons adjacent to oxygen atoms. A multiplet signal around δ 7-8 and a singlet at δ 10.48 appear for the aromatic and aldehydic protons respectively. The integral peak heights are in accord with the proposed assignments.

The macrocycle (**1**) gives two signals at δ 2.8 and 3.6 as triplets due to inequivalent methylene protons of the amine linkage. The former signal is assigned to the methylene protons adjacent to secondary nitrogen atom of NH groups, and the latter, more downfield signal, is for the methylene protons adjacent to the imine groups. The effect of deshielding is reflected for the N=CH groups because of its conjugation with phenyl rings. The signal for aldehydic proton disappears from this position and another signal appears at δ 8.69 as a singlet due to HC=N proton. The signal for two equivalent methylene protons (O- CH_2) occurs as a singlet at a slightly upfield region at δ 4.3. The

TABLE 1—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF PRECURSOR DIALDEHYDES AND MACROCYCLIC LIGANDS

Compd.	Chemical shift ^a (δ)
1,4-Bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,4-dioxabutane	4.54 (s, CH ₂), 7-8 (m, Ar), 10.4 (s, CHO)
1,5-Bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,5-dioxapentane	2.45 (q, CH ₂), 4.3 (t, CH ₂), 7.8 (m, Ar), 10.48 (s, CHO)
Bzo ₂ [17]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂	2.8 and 3.6 (t, =N-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -N=), 4.3 (s, O-CH ₂), 6.7-7.8 (m, Ar), 8.69 (s, CH=N)
Bzo ₂ [18]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂	2.3 (q, CH ₂), 4.2 (t, CH ₂), 6.7-7.8 (m, Ar), 2.9 and 3.65 (t, =N-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -N=), 8.65 (s, CH=N)

^aAll resonances in ppm downfield from TMS, CDCl₃ used as solvent.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF MACROCYCLIC COMPLEXES (1-8) IN AQUEOUS DMF

Compd.	$-E_{1/2}^{\text{I,II}}$ V	I_d μA	n	$-E_{1/2}^{\text{I,II}}$ V
Ni[Bzo ₂ [17]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]Br ₂	1.045	2.1	1.0	1.398
Ni[Bzo ₂ [17]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]I ₂	1.080	2.3	1.0	1.395
Ni[Bzo ₂ [17]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1.042	2.2	1.05	1.410
Ni Bzo ₂ [18]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]Br ₂	1.090	2.8	1.05	1.415
Ni[Bzo ₂ [18]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]I ₂	1.074	2.2	1.0	1.420
Ni[Bzo ₂ [18]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1.065	2.3	1.0	1.418
Ni Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]Br ₂	1.110	2.5	1.0	1.665
Ni[Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]I ₂	1.118	2.0	1.0	1.650
Ni[Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1.080	2.2	1.05	1.645
Ni[Bzo ₂ [15]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]Br ₂	1.120	2.4	1.25	1.660
Ni[Bzo ₂ [15]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]I ₂	1.130	2.6	1.0	1.660
Ni Bzo ₂ [15]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1.128	2.2	1.0	1.658
Ni[MeBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]Br ₂	1.080	2.4	1.1	1.600
Ni[MeBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]I ₂	1.062	2.6	1.03	1.550
Ni[MeBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1.068	2.6	1.0	1.570
Ni[MeBzo ₂ [15]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]Br ₂	1.100	2.2	1.05	1.650
Ni[MeBzo ₂ [15]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂]I ₂	1.180	2.2	1.14	1.670
Ni[MeBzo ₂ [15]tetraeneN ₂ O ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1.085	2.0	1.0	1.645
Ni[Bzo ₂ [14]pentaeneN ₂ O ₂]Br ₂	1.154	2.2	1.1	1.625
Ni[Bzo ₂ [14]pentaeneN ₂ O ₂]I ₂	1.152	2.4	1.0	1.625
Ni[Bzo ₂ [14]pentaeneN ₂ O ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1.153	2.1	1.15	1.626
Ni[Bzo ₂ [15]pentaeneN ₂ O ₂]Br ₂	1.165	2.5	1.19	1.655
Ni[Bzo ₂ [15]pentaeneN ₂ O ₂]I ₂	1.185	2.2	1.0	1.657
Ni[Bzo ₂ [15]pentaeneN ₂ O ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1.190	2.2	1.109	1.658

aromatic protons give signals as a multiplet around δ 6.7-7.8.

The macrocycle (2) gives two signals at δ 2.3 and 4.2 as a quintet and a triplet respectively. These two signals are slightly upfield in comparison with the original present precursor intermediate and has been assigned to methylene protons. Two other signals at δ 2.9 and 3.65 appear as triplets and can be assigned for the inequivalent methylene protons of the amine groups. The signal at δ 8.65 which occurs as a singlet and the signal at δ 6.7-7.8 appearing as a multiplet are due to CH=N and aromatic protons respectively. The integral peak heights agree with the proposed structures.

The nmr spectra of the macrocycles (3-8) have been examined and the results resemble the spectral data reported by Lindoy and coworkers.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties: All the complexes possess magnetic moments in the range 3.3-3.46 B.M. (at 300 K) and manifest a spin-

triplet ground state for the nickel(II) ion. Electronic spectra of the macrocycles in DMF exhibit three bands in the range 15 000-35 000 cm⁻¹. The low energy band is relatively less intense, slightly asymmetric and broad; at half-height of the band it has the width nearly 4 000 cm⁻¹. The bands near 27 000 cm⁻¹ are relatively more intense and sharp. The highest frequency band near 32 000 cm⁻¹ has a Gaussian shape. The spectra, on the whole, resemble the spectral features of nickel(II) ion under an octahedral symmetry, and the first two bands near 18 000 and 27 000 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the transitions ³T_{1g}(F) ← ³A_{1g} and ³T_{1g}(P) ← ³A_{1g} respectively.}}}}

Electrochemical studies: The electrochemical data studied polarographically for the present series of complexes in DMF-water medium (80:20, v/v) and with tetraethylammonium perchlorate as the supporting electrolyte at an ionic strength of 0.1 M are recorded in Table 2.

The nickel(II) macrocyclic complexes undergo reductions in two steps which are reversible at the dropping mercury electrode and the reduction processes are diffusion-controlled. Estimated values (Table 2) of diffusion current (I_d) and number of electrons transferred (n) indicate that each redox process is accompanied by the transfer of one electron.

The role of ligand structure on the thermodynamic parameter $E_{1/2}$ for the redox processes is spectacular. The plots of $E_{1/2}$ values for the macrocycles 1–4 along the ordinate and the ligand atomicity along the abscissa are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 for the first and second redox waves respectively. The ligand atomicity is defined aptly as the ring size of the macrocycle, i.e. the number of carbon, nitrogen and oxygen atoms present in the chain of the macrocyclic ligand. The graphic plots candidly demonstrate the effect of the size of the macro-ring on the redox potentials.

Fig. 1. Plots of $-E_{1/2}$ for macrocyclic complexes vs ligand atomicity (number of C, N and O in the ring): (○) I^- , (△) ClO_4^- and (●) Br^- .

For the first step of reduction the redox potential ($E_{1/2}$) values range from -1.04 to -1.13 V. The 15-membered macrocyclic complexes are most stable towards reduction and nearly 30–40 mV more cathodic than the 14-membered macrocycles irrespective of the anion. The $E_{1/2}$ values for the 17-membered macrocyclic complexes are most anodic. The $E_{1/2}$ vs atomicity curves are, in general, in the form of a 'tilde' for each kind of anion salt, i.e. bromide, iodide and perchlorate respectively.

The macrocyclic complexes 1 and 2 have N_3O_3 and 3 and 4 have N_2O_4 type of coordination environments. Since all these complexes exhibit

spectral and magnetic features characteristic of octahedral nickel(II), the octahedral coordination is completed by an additional pair of halide or water molecules in case of N_3O_3 ligands and a halide ion or a water molecule in case N_2O_4 type ligands, the N_3O_3 occupying coordination sites at the corners of a square-pyramid.

The electrochemical data show that the redox behaviour is predominantly influenced by the ring size of the macrocycle rather than the nucleophilic character of the ligating atoms. Similar 'tilde' shapes are observed for the second step of reduction and again pronounce the effect of the macrocyclic ring size. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs atomicity^{15,16} is shown in Fig. 2 for this step of reduction and the plots show close proximity for the bromide, iodide and perchlorate salts. Independent determination of ligand reduction shows a polarographic wave corresponding to $E_{1/2}$ value in the same region as the corresponding complexes and unequivocally demonstrates that this step of reduction arises due to ligand based reduction delocalised over the complex species.

Fig. 2. Plots of $-E_{1/2}$ for macrocyclic complexes vs ligand atomicity (number of C, N and O in the ring): (○) I^- , (△) ClO_4^- and (●) Br^- .

A large number of tetraaza macrocyclic complexes have been the subject of electrochemical studies and the effect of ring size has been examined. The general pattern of redox behaviour on ring size are similar and the relative values of $E_{1/2}$ lie in the order, (14) < (15) > (16) > (17), the redox potentials for 15-membered rings lie most cathodic for similar structures.

The relative magnitude of $E_{1/2}$ values of N_3O_3 and N_2O_4 macrocycles compared with the $E_{1/2}$ values for N_4 and N_5 macrocycles of similar (not necessarily identical) ring size and relative degree of unsaturation indicate the stability of the macrocycles

towards electron transfer reactions. There are examples of nickel(II) tetraaza macrocycle complexes¹⁶ which show two reversible or quasi-reversible one-electron two-step reduction waves and the first step is located near -1.0 V. The complexes of the present series show the corresponding $E_{1/2}$ values in the proximity of this region and seem to have comparable stability.

The effect of ligand structure on the thermodynamic parameter $E_{1/2}$ for the macrocyclic complexes 3-8 is clearly pronounced (Table 2). The $E_{1/2}$ values for 3-6 are not appreciably different in spite of the fact that the latter pair of macrocycles contain a methyl group on the backbone of the ligand. However, the $E_{1/2}$ values for 7 and 8 are discernibly more cathodic and reflect the effect of the benzenoid group. This behaviour is reminiscent of the thermodynamic behaviour of a series of cyclopean ligands^{17,18} where the structures of the macro-rings have been modified incorporating ethylenediimine and *o*-phenylenediimine components. The relatively higher value of the redox parameter $E_{1/2}$ appears to arise due to a higher degree of conjugation in the macro-ring and consequent contraction in ring size.

References

1. G. A. MERTSON, "Coordination Chemistry of Macrocyclic Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1977, p. 8, and references therein.
2. G. W. GOKEL and S. H. KORZENIOWSKI, "Macrocyclic Polyether Syntheses", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1982.
3. C. J. PEDERSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2495, 7017.
4. C. J. PEDERSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 891.
5. W. OLEGG, J. C. LOCKHART and F. H. MUSA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1986, **47**.
6. U. CASELLATO, P. GUERRIERO, S. TAMBURINI, P. A. VIGATO and R. GRAZIANI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **119**, 215.
7. L. G. ARMSTRONG and L. F. LINDOY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 1322.
8. L. F. LINDOY, H. C. LIP, L. F. POWER and J. H. REA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 1724.
9. L. G. ARMSTRONG, L. F. LINDOY, M. MCPARTLIN, G. M. MOCKLER and P. A. TASKER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 1665.
10. L. G. ARMSTRONG, P. G. GRIMSLEY, L. F. LINDOY, H. C. LIP, V. A. NORRIS and R. J. SMITH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 2350.
11. L. DAIZHENG, Z. J. ZHONG, H. OKAWA and S. KIDA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **118**, 21.
12. R. S. PAREDES, N. S. VALERA and L. F. LINDOY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1986, **39**, 1071.
13. B. SAHOO, N. C. PATRA, A. K. ROUT and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 680, and references therein.
14. B. SAHOO, A. K. ROUT, N. C. PATRA and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem.*, in the press.
15. L. FABBRIZZI, A. POGGI and P. ZANELLO, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1495.
16. J. LEWIS and N. SCHRODER, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1982, 1085.
17. B. SAHOO, J. CHAKRABARTI and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 209.
18. B. SAHOO and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **22**, 560.